

Spectrophotometric study of adsorption of bromo thymol blue on charcoal and phosphates of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II}

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The adsorption behaviour of bromo thymol blue on charcoal and phosphates of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} has been investigated spectrophotometrically in aqueous alkaline medium of pH 9.6 at $\lambda_{\max} = 617$ nm. The adsorption data have been fitted to the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The adsorption behaviour of adsorbents has been compared and aluminium phosphate has been found to be the most effective among the phosphate adsorbents

Palit and Moulik¹ have studied adsorption behaviour of cationic dyes, ethidium bromide (EB) and methylene blue (MB) individually as well as from their 1 : 1 [mol/mol] binary mixture on negative surface of silica in aqueous medium. The effects of temperature, the salt KCl and pH on the adsorption process have also been examined.

Treatment of waste water containing dyes²⁻⁴ by adsorption is an emerging field of research. The process of adsorption has an edge over other methods due to its sludge-free clean operation and complete removal of dyes even from the dilute solutions. The commonly used adsorbent for dye removal by adsorption is activated carbon⁵. However, commercially available activated carbons are very expensive. Therefore, there is need to produce low-cost and effective activated carbons. This has prompted Singh and Srivastava⁶ to undertake studies on the adsorption vis-à-vis basic dyes removal from waste water using activated carbon derived from H₃PO₄ impregnated rice husk.

Parida and Mishra⁷⁻⁹ have studied the adsorption of monochromophoric, bischromophoric and styryl pyridium dyes on silica, alkali treated silica, PEG and CTAB treated silica surfaces. Sumanjit and Prasad¹⁰ have studied the adsorption of a number of acid dyes in aqueous solutions using rice husk ash as the adsorbent.

From the above stated survey of literature it appears that the adsorption of sulfonphthalein dyes on different adsorbents has not been studied so far. Hence the adsorption of bromo thymol blue, a sulfonphthalein dye, has been studied spectrophotometrically using charcoal and phosphates of some metal ions, viz. Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} as adsorbents.

Results and discussion

Determination of λ_{\max} :

The absorption spectrum of bromo thymol blue in aqueous alkaline medium of pH 9.6 reveals that maximum absorption occurs at wavelength 617 nm. Solutions of bromo thymol blue with varying concentrations from 0.25×10^{-5} to 4.0×10^{-5} M were prepared and their absorbance was determined keeping the wavelength constant at λ_{\max} of 617 nm. The plot of absorbance against the concentration was a straight-line passing through the origin, which confirms that the Beer-Lambert's law is obeyed. This calibration plot was used to determine the equilibrium concentration of the dye solutions obtained after the adsorption of the dye by different adsorbents, viz. charcoal, phosphates of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II}.

Effect of the dose of different adsorbents :

The adsorption of bromo thymol blue, as a function of the dose (amount) of different adsorbents, has been studied¹¹ by keeping the concentration and pH of the dye constant at 0.5×10^{-5} M and 9.6, respectively in each case.

The plots showing percent adsorption of the dye as a function of dose (amount) of each adsorbent have been depicted in typical Fig.1. From this figure it is seen that the adsorption of the dye increases with the dose of each adsorbent until it attains a limiting value at a particular dose beyond which there is no effect¹² of the dose of the adsorbent on the adsorption of the dye. From this figure the optimum amount of each adsorbent has been obtained as mentioned below : charcoal = 0.02 g, aluminium phosphate = 0.1 g, iron phosphate = 0.4 g, chromium phosphate = 0.5 g, zinc phosphate = 0.5 g.

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Fig. 1. Effect of dose of adsorbent on the adsorption of bromo thymol blue in alkaline aqueous medium of pH 9.6 : (O) chromium phosphate, (Δ) iron phosphate.

Freundlich isotherm :

The adsorption data have been fitted to the Freundlich isotherm

$$\log \frac{x}{m} = \log k + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e$$

where x and m are the mass of adsorbate and adsorbent respectively, C_e is the equilibrium concentration and k and n are the empirical constants of the Freundlich isotherm.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$ according to Freundlich isotherm for bromo thymol blue in alkaline aqueous medium of pH 9.6 with optimum amount of adsorbent : (O) plot with 0.02 g charcoal, (Δ) plot with 0.1 g aluminium phosphate.

From the plots of $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$ (Fig. 2), the constants k and n were obtained and these values have been listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of Freundlich parameters

Adsorbents	Slope	Intercept	n	k
Charcoal	0.756	0.175	1.322	1.496
Iron phosphate	0.900	-0.500	1.110	0.316
Aluminium phosphate	1.210	0.075	0.826	1.188
Chromium phosphate	1.058	-0.550	1.059	0.281
Zinc phosphate	0.857	-0.447	1.166	0.333

It has been reported by Sumanjit and Prasad¹⁰ that the adsorption capacity of an adsorbent for the given adsorbate (dye) is given by the constant k . A perusal of this table shows that the values of constant k for the adsorbents used in this study followed the order :

$$k_{\text{Charcoal}} > k_{\text{AlPO}_4} > k_{\text{Zn}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2} > k_{\text{FePO}_4} > k_{\text{CrPO}_4}$$

A perusal of the value of n for different adsorbents shows that the reciprocal of this constant (i.e. slope of $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$) is a measure of binding ability of an adsorbate on an adsorbent. From the values of n (vide Table 1) it is seen that n is greater than one in the case of the adsorbents : charcoal, Fe, Cr and Zn phosphates, while it is less than one in the case of Al phosphate. It is reported in literature¹³ that a value of n greater than unity signifies that the forces within the surface layer are attractive. On the other hand, a fractional value of n indicates a repulsive interaction between adsorbed species. In the light of this view point, the adsorption of bromo thymol blue on charcoal, Fe phosphate, Cr phosphate and Zn phosphate involves attractive forces between the species of bromo thymol blue whereas its adsorption on Al phosphate involves repulsive interaction between the adsorbed species.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of bromo thymol blue of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was prepared in alkaline aqueous solution of pH 9.6. Solutions of different molarities were prepared by the dilution of the stock solution. The absorption spectrum of bromo thymol blue was recorded by using Elico-SL-159 UV-VIS spectro-photometer at $0.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ and at different wavelengths. From these spectra the maximum absorption was found to occur at 617 nm. Therefore, the entire study of the adsorption was performed at this wavelength. The adsorption study was carried out by taking an optimum amount of each adsorbent, i.e. charcoal and phosphates of metals in stoppered bottles containing solutions of the dye of different concentrations but having the same pH of 9.6. The stoppered bottles were then shaken in an electrical shaker for 1 h. The contents of the bottles were next filtered and the absorption spectra of the filtrates were recorded under the same experimental conditions as were maintained in the absence of adsorbents.

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